

ISic3468

I.Sicily inscription 3468

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Gaulus

Place of origin (modern)

Gozo

Provenance

Victoria, either on the city gate, or in the castle

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Victoria, Gozo, Museo archeologico nazionale (Cittadella)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR113430

1. M(arco) Vallio C(ai) f(ilio) Quir(ina) Rufo equo pu
2. blico exornato a Divo Antoni
3. no Aug(usto) Pio plebs Gaulitana ex
4. aere conlato ob merita et in
5. solacium C(ai) Valli Postumi patroni municipii
6. patris eius
7. [C(aius) Vallius Postumus p] ater
0. [[---]--]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285172

EDR 113430
EDCS 22100627

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7508 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bruno, B. 2004. L'arcipelago maltese in età romana e bizantina. Attività economiche e scambi al centro del Mediterraneo. Bari. At 20, 57

Christol, M., Pirino, E. 2006. Une famille de notables dans l'île de Gaulos (Gozo). In Akerraz, A., Ruggeri, P., Siraj, A., Vismara, C.(eds.), *L'Africa Romana 16*. Sassari. pp. 2599-2626. At 2610-2614

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3468. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388622>